

Blockchain Technology for Deep Learning Applications: a Systematic Mapping Study

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a systematic mapping study on the use of blockchain technology in deep learning applications. The study aims to map the current state of research and highlight potential areas for future work. In particular, we are interested in analyzing the types of research conducted, the most common application domains, and the expected benefits and reasons that motivate the use of blockchain. We selected more than a thousand articles from digital libraries and applied inclusion-exclusion criteria to select relevant studies, which were then analyzed according to a structured methodology. The result of the analysis provides an overview of the research area from different perspectives.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Computing methodologies** → **Machine learning; Distributed artificial intelligence**; • **Computer systems organization** → **Neural networks**.

KEYWORDS

Blockchain, Deep Learning, Federated Learning

1 INTRODUCTION

Deep learning is a rapidly growing field that has led to significant advances in areas such as image and speech recognition, natural language processing, and autonomous systems. However, deep learning models often involve collecting and processing large amounts of sensitive data, which raises critical privacy and security concerns. Blockchain technology, which is a decentralized and distributed ledger system, has the potential to address these concerns by providing a secure, trusted, and transparent way to store and share data and models.

Several studies have been published in recent years exploring the use of blockchain technology for deep learning applications in multiple domains. This systematic mapping study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the combination of these technologies.

2 RELATED WORK

In this section, we review the existing literature on the use of blockchain for deep learning applications. In particular, we aim to highlight the differences between existing studies and this work.

Salah *et al.* [3] discuss how blockchain can be combined with artificial intelligence, presenting different applications and use cases. They also provide an overview of the open research challenges in combining the two technologies. They consider papers published until 2018.

Zhang *et al.* [6] present and discuss emerging research topics that involve deep learning and blockchain. In particular, they cover five application domains: infrastructure, finance and trade, transportation and logistics, smart contracts, and information security. They consider articles published between 2018 and 2020.

Shafay *et al.* [4] discuss open challenges and opportunities in combining deep learning and blockchain. They propose a review of blockchain-based deep learning frameworks targeting different application domains. They consider articles published until 2021.

Taherdoost [5] proposes a critical review of blockchain and AI, covering application domains, benefits, and challenges of combining these two technologies. Taherdoost considers only articles from the Scopus library with years of publication ranging from 2012 to 2018.

Differently from the reported studies, we consider multiple libraries (IEEE, Science Direct, ACM) and articles published after 2016. We focus on application domains, areas of interest, and motivations leading the combination of deep learning and blockchain.

3 BACKGROUND

3.1 Deep Learning

Deep learning is a class of machine learning that uses artificial neural networks (ANNs) to learn and make predictions from data. These networks are made up of multiple layers, which is why they are referred to as "deep" learning networks.

Deep learning models are trained and deployed to solve multiple problems, reaching a super-human performance. Some current applications of deep learning include:

- **Computer Vision:** identify objects, people, and activities in images and videos.
- **Speech Recognition:** convert spoken words to text.
- **Natural Language Processing:** understand and generate human-like language.
- **Robotics:** control the movement and perception of robots.
- **Healthcare:** analyze medical images and predict patient outcomes.
- **Finance:** detect fraudulent transactions and predict stock prices.
- **Self-driving cars:** navigate and make decisions on the road.

3.2 Blockchain

Blockchain technology is a decentralized, distributed ledger system that uses cryptography to secure and validate transactions. Each transaction is defined as a "block," hence blockchain. This technology allows the creation of a secure and immutable digital register of transactions replicated across a network of computers (nodes) without the need for a central authority. This property

makes blockchain resistant to tampering or hacking and enables multiple applications such as digital currencies and supply chain management.

Given its decentralized nature, agreements between nodes are managed autonomously through smart contracts. A smart contract is a self-executing contract where the terms of the agreement are written directly into lines of code. These contracts can be stored and replicated on the blockchain network and can be used to facilitate, verify, and enforce the negotiation or execution of a transaction. Smart contracts enable the automation of a wide range of processes, reduce the need for intermediaries, increase transparency and trust, and facilitate the execution of complex transactions.

Transactions generated by the execution of smart contracts must be validated before being added to the chain. A consensus protocol serves this purpose. A consensus protocol is a mechanism by which nodes in a blockchain network reach agreement on the state of the ledger. Different consensus protocols have specific characteristics like power efficiency, security, and scalability. The most widely used consensus protocols are proof of work (PoW) and proof of stake (PoS). PoW, used by Bitcoin, validates transactions by asking nodes to compute complex mathematical problems. PoS, used by Ethereum, validates transactions based on the stake (the amount of cryptocurrency a node holds) of the validating node.

3.3 Blockchain for Deep Learning

Blockchain-based deep learning represents the combination of blockchain technology and deep learning. These technologies allow for securing, validating, and trusting data used in deep learning, enabling secure and decentralized sharing of trained models. This field is new and emerging, with potential applications such as secure distributed systems and privacy-preserving AI.

4 RESEARCH METHOD

This section describes the methodology adopted to conduct the mapping study. The first subsection proposes and motivates the research questions driving this work, while the second subsection reports on the complete selection process.

4.1 Research Questions

Table 1 reports and motivates the research questions considered for the review. These questions focus on the timing, types, application domains, and advantages of blockchain and deep learning.

4.2 Research Strategy

This study follows the method depicted in Figure 1 adapted from the one proposed by Peterson *et al.* [2].

We used three digital libraries to extract the articles for this study: Science Direct, ACM, and IEEE. Table 2 reports the search queries and the number of articles obtained.

The screening and selection process consisted of multiple steps. First, duplicates are removed and then the following inclusion and exclusion criteria are applied:

Inclusion Criteria

- Studies published after 2016 (first date).
- Studies in the field of Computer Science.
- Studies strictly related to the research topic.

Exclusion Criteria

- Studies not in English.
- Studies not accessible in full-text.
- Duplicated studies.
- Studies not related to the research topic.
- Studies that are systematic mappings or reviews.

Next, we reviewed the included and excluded items. Figure 2 depicts the selection process pipeline. We classified a total of 1446 articles. Of these, we selected 246 as relevant. Selected articles underwent a process of data extraction to answer the research questions. Specifically, we extracted a set of keywords for each question. We then processed and visualized the resulting data with the Python programming language.

4.3 Reliability of Inclusion Decisions

Since the study selection stage involves judgment by the researcher, we used Cohen's K statistic, Cohen *et al.* [1], to measure the reliability of inclusions. Specifically, another researcher performed the inclusion operation on a sample of ten articles. The obtained K=1 value indicates complete agreement. Table 3 in the appendix contains the articles used as a test.

5 RESULTS

5.1 RQ1 - In what year where the articles published?

Figure 3 reports the number of articles published each year. Notably, the combination of blockchain and deep learning is discussed for the first time in 2018, with only ten publications. In subsequent years this number grows steadily, reaching 102 publications in 2022. This rapid growth indicates that interest in combining blockchain technology and artificial intelligence is increasing.

In 2023, at the date of writing this research, 3 articles have already been published.

5.2 RQ2 - What are the types of research?

Figure 4 reports the most adopted research approaches when discussing blockchain and deep learning. We used the classification scheme presented by Peterson *et al.* [2].

Most articles fall in the "Solution Proposal" category because they all describe the use of blockchain and deep learning technologies to address specific problems or challenges in various fields, such as healthcare, construction equipment security, and IoT-enabled systems. These papers propose solutions, methodologies, and frameworks rather than evaluating or validating existing solutions or discussing philosophical or opinion-based topics.

The fact that most of the articles fall into the "Solution Proposal" category suggests that combining blockchain and deep learning allows for solving multiple real-world problems.

Only two articles belong to the "Evaluation Research" category.

5.3 RQ3 - What is the application domain of the proposed solutions?

Figure 5 represents the general application domains in which a combination of blockchain and deep learning is employed. Most

Table 1: Research Questions

RQ#	Research Question	Motivation
RQ1	In what year were the articles published?	To provide a temporal analysis.
RQ2	What are the types of research?	To analyze the types of research conducted.
RQ3	What is the application domain of the proposed solutions?	To identify the topics in which the research is active.
RQ4	What is the focus of the proposed solutions?	To identify more specific fields of application.
RQ5	Why use blockchain technology?	To identify expected benefits and reasons motivating the use of blockchain.

Process Steps

Outcomes

Figure 1: Diagram of the research process.

Table 2: Digital Library Queries

Library	Query	Paper#
Science Direct	blockchain AND ("deep learning" OR "machine learning")	245
ACM	(Title:(blockchain AND "deep learning") OR Title:(blockchain AND "machine learning")) OR (Abstract:(blockchain AND "deep learning") OR Abstract:(blockchain AND "machine learning"))	82
IEEE	("All Metadata":blockchain) AND ("All Metadata":"machine learning" OR "All Metadata": "deep learning")	1119

of the articles present solutions that suit different application domains. Immediately following are solutions involving healthcare and medicine, internet and networking, transportation, safety and security, and business and finance. Healthcare represents the area where most of the studies are focused.

The following list represents the subcategories contained in each application domain:

- **Healthcare and Biomedics:** healthcare, biomedics, animal health, pharmaceutical.
- **Environment and Agriculture:** environment, energy, garbage management, agriculture.
- **Research and Education:** research process, knowledge capital, misinformation detection, fake news, clickbait detection.
- **Transportation:** railways, mobility.
- **Industrial Automation:** manufacturing, industry 4.0, fault detection.

- **Business and Finance:** data market, customer services, enterprise, finance, insurance, service provisioning.
- **Safety and Security:** public security, cybersecurity, construction safety, fraud detection, identity management.
- **Internet and Networks:** IoT, IoV, AIoT, edge computing, fog computing, network traffic, CPSSs&CPSs, telecommunications, reputation systems.
- **Misc:** image auditing, predictive behaviour, UAVs, autonomous vehicle, tourism, device personalization, 3D printing, electronic voting, drones&satellites, smart identification, resource management, biometric recognition.

5.4 RQ4 - What is the focus of the proposed solutions?

In contrast to RQ3, the purpose of this section is to provide a more detailed overview of possible application domains and solutions.

Figure 2: Diagram of the selection process.

Figure 4: Research Types Facets.

Figure 3: Publications per year.

Figure 5: Blockchain and Deep Learning application domains.

Figure 6 shows the top ten microcategories in which solutions were proposed: Healthcare consistently ranks first, followed by mobility, the Internet of Things, and cybersecurity. Figure 7 shows some more

specific solutions proposed. In healthcare, the most popular topics concern patient data sharing and disease detection or prediction. In the mobility industry, most articles focus on vehicular networks, traffic management, autonomous vehicles, and autonomous driving.

Figure 6: Research Focus (Top Ten).

Figure 8: Blockchain properties.

Figure 7: Detailed Applications (Top Ten).

Figure 9: Application Domain vs Publication Year.

5.5 RQ5 - Why use blockchain technology?

The use of blockchain technology can bring many benefits in terms of privacy and trust, as well as enable a decentralized computing strategy, increasing security systems and applications.

Figure 8 represents the properties that lead to the choice of blockchain technology. Trust and security of data and models come first, indicating how important it is to verify and certify the provenance of data and learning models. Decentralization and privacy also play a fundamental role.

5.6 Mapping

This section aims to combine some of the dimensions analyzed previously. Figure 9, which maps application domains and publication years, shows increased interest in application domains regarding healthcare, the internet, and networks. General solutions are also rapidly growing. Less significant growth is also present in other application domains, such as safety, security, environment, and agriculture. Figure 10 shows the need to implement increasingly secure and verified applications that respect user privacy and ensure

Figure 10: Blockchain Properties vs Publication Year.

integrity has increased in recent years. Ensuring these properties is essential in applications that collect and use data about users, especially in cases of sensitive information. Figure 11 shows which

Figure 11: Application Domain vs Blockchain Properties.

properties of blockchain technology are most frequently mentioned in different application domains. From the chart, we conclude that trust and security are the most requested properties, particularly in applications involving health, the internet, networks, and transportation. These two properties are also cited in multi-domain applications. In applications involving health, privacy is mentioned most, highlighting the confidentiality of medical data.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study identifies that interest in combining blockchain technology and artificial intelligence (deep learning, machine learning, and federated learning) is increasing rapidly. The number of publications on this topic has grown steadily, starting with only ten publications in 2018 and reaching 102 articles in 2022.

Most analyzed papers fall into the "Solution Proposal" category, indicating that combining blockchain and deep learning allows for solving multiple real-world problems. Healthcare, internet and networking, transportation, safety and security, and business and finance represent the application domains in which most studies are focused, with healthcare in the first place.

The choice to use blockchain is supported by the necessity for modern applications to embrace properties such as trust, security, decentralization, and privacy. These qualities are critical and desirable, especially when users data is involved.

In conclusion, blockchain technology can improve applications and systems by making them decentralized, secure, and trustable. Integrating blockchain with artificial intelligence solutions can therefore bring benefits in several application domains. In the future, we expect more and more solutions to take advantage of the numerous benefits that blockchain can bring to existing and new applications.

7 ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

The Bibliography file containing all the 264 papers considered in this work is available online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8042108>.

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* the complete bibliography is available in "Additional Materials".

Table 3: Inclusion Reliability Table

Title	DOI	Researcher A	Researcher B
A Demonstration of Sterling: A Privacy-Preserving Data Marketplace	10.14778/3229863.3236266	yes	yes
Towards Open and Automated Customer Service: A Blockchain-based AutoML Framework	10.1145/3207677.3277939	yes	yes
A Unified Analytical Framework for Trustable Machine Learning and Automation Running with Blockchain	10.1109/BigData.2018.8622262	yes	yes
When Machine Learning Meets Blockchain: A Decentralized, Privacy-preserving and Secure Design	10.1109/BigData.2018.8622598	yes	yes
On Enabling Machine Learning Tasks atop Public Blockchains: A Crowdsourcing Approach	10.1109/ICDMW.2018.00019	yes	yes
Machine Learning for Secure Device Personalization Using Blockchain	10.1109/ICACCI.2018.8554476	yes	yes
Blockchain-based Personal Health Data Sharing System Using Cloud Storage	10.1109/HealthCom.2018.8531125	yes	yes
Leveraging blockchain for retraining deep learning architecture in patient-specific arrhythmia classification	10.1109/BHI.2018.8333451	yes	yes
DInEMMo: Decentralized Incentivization for Enterprise Marketplace Models	10.1109/HiPCW.2018.8634320	yes	yes
Improving Identity Management of Cloud-Based IoT Applications Using Blockchain	10.1109/ICIAS.2018.8540564	yes	yes